

Catalyzing Open and Collaborative Science to Address Development Challenges

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INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH CENTRE (IDRC-CRDI)

by

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In this interim report, we provide updates on major developments within OCSDNet since our last annual technical report, submitted to IDRC in June 2016. Rather than duplicating the more detailed and structured format of the annual report, we are highlighting the key initiatives and their progress, and point to future directions of these developments. The key headings that follow indicate the areas of most intense development and the results that are emerging. We conclude with observations on gaps in our research and how we plan to address them.

1. Open Science Manifesto

The production of the ‘Open and Collaborative Science Manifesto’ is coming to its final stage. After several iterations with OCSDNet advisors and network members, we have produced a final narrative (in English) that reflects and articulates the collective vision of our members and the set of principles that guide their thinking and practice of Open Science in Development. Over the last four months, in the spirit of making the findings of OCSDNet research as accessible as possible to multiple audiences, we have collaborated with the female-led Design Co-operative from Argentina [‘Cooperativa de Diseño’](#) to produce a graphic representation and a three minute video of the Manifesto. Next steps include translating the Manifesto into five languages: Spanish, French, Arabic, Russian and Afrikaans, so sub-grantees can share this resource with relevant regional networks, as well as partner institutions and organizations as part of their advocacy strategies. Our goal is to launch the online dissemination of the Manifesto online by February-March 2017, and conduct an analysis of the circulation and uptake of these resources.

2. Internal Evaluation and Communications Midterm Report

Although currently we are a few months beyond the ‘mid-term’ mark of the network’s project timeline, the coordination team felt it would be useful to undertake a team-oriented reflective assessment of the extent to which we have progressed towards the achievement of our Key Evaluation Questions (KEQ) and Communications Objectives (CO) that were established last year, through our partnership with DECI mentors. As such, a ‘Mid-term’ Evaluation Report has been compiled, which collectively helps to define some of our key strengths and weaknesses as a Network Coordination Team, while articulating key lessons, successes and new, emerging questions.

We are currently entering a transition period, whereby, in the next few months, many of the network projects will be coming to an end and a period of research analysis and dissemination will begin. As many of our KEQs and COs have been centred around the creation of an inclusive space for the projects to share, learn and engage with one another, we recognise that our priority, going forward, will be instead to evaluate/communicate the outcomes and impact of the projects and network as a whole.

Thus, the last section of the report outlines some new KEQs and COs which will be used to guide our actions over the next year.

The full report can be accessed below:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HMKhFApOj7c6-bLlMiwy8_919V4g_8DiRn90kjGMlaU/edit#heading=h.d2a0o1vpfyxy

3. Contextualizing Openness Book Publication

‘Contextualising Openness’ will be a collective publication, with case-study chapters submitted from all OCSDNet projects, and section summaries written by network advisors. Working across an incredibly diverse group of individuals, we have recognised that openness is a nuanced and complex concept and process. While it has been embraced by some cultures, others have been more reluctant to unrestricted knowledge sharing without considering the power relations, inequalities and structural conditions that shape knowledge production. The intention of this publication will be for each of the OCSDNet teams to reflect on the nature of their respective contexts - including the political, economic, social and historical factors that have coalesced to influence the way that their project and region has interacted with the concept of openness, creating spaces in which understandings of and reactions to openness navigate a spectrum of caution and embracement.

At present, all 12 teams have submitted first drafts of their chapters, and preliminary review process by the coordination team has been completed. We have now moved on to internal peer-review, whereby each author will openly review two other chapters in their thematic section, to provide feedback around the content, structure and conceptual framing of each chapter. Our goal is to launch the final publication in June 2017, during our final network meeting.

See here for a link to the current draft chapters:

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/0B_98nOGokJVWYVg1THNINFB3Uk0

4. IDRC Inclusive Openness Chapter

We are excited to be contributing to IDRC’s ‘Inclusive Openness’ publication, with practical examples of the barriers and possibilities for Open Science to be made more inclusive, in order to sustainably address local development challenges. At present, we have written a chapter outline and undertaken a preliminary literature review in order to contribute towards this publication. Our draft document can be accessed [here](#).

Ultimately, our aim in writing this chapter is to bridge the gap between decades of development literature that recognise the importance of inclusive, non-extractive and participatory research with ever-growing conversations around Open Science. At present, most open science discussions are focused on the technology, tools and processes for making science ‘open,’ but fail to look at issues of power, access and language that prevent these tools/spaces from being truly ‘inclusive.’

Our framing of inclusion is grounded in action and reaction. It is a process (not an end goal) that progresses solely through disruption and realignment of the status quo. It is the intentional movement of power from those who have to those who are historically marginalised from knowledge production

processes. It is only with this intentional realignment, we suggest, that open science can create transformative opportunities for community development.

In terms of timeline, our intention is to have a complete draft ready by the end of January 2017. Leslie (and hopefully Becky) will be attending the Cape Town writers' workshop in March 2017.

5. Recent Network-Related Events

OpenCon 2016

Last year, a contingent of highly motivated early-career researchers from within OCSDNet applied to OpenCon2015 from various countries throughout the Global South. Despite excellent applications, all were rejected due to the high costs associated with travelling to Europe for the event. As a result, the vast majority of participants at the 2015 event were from Euro-North American countries.

As OpenCon supposedly encourages and promotes 'diversity' and 'cross-disciplinary learning' between young and active leaders, we viewed this rejection of Southern candidates as quite discriminatory, resulting in a context where only a limited perspective of openness is explored. Consequently, we emailed OpenCon organisers to highlight this issue.

This year, two representatives from the network (Denisse and Thomas) were able to attend OpenCon 2016, and the organisers stressed that they had put careful attention towards funding travel for Southern participants. In addition, this year's discussions were much more critical of power dimensions in knowledge-production processes (and the North-South divide); which was very promising for a wider and more inclusive understanding of Open Science in the mainstream scientific community. In some part, we attribute these changes to the lobbying done by OCSDNet last year.

More recently, Leslie Chan presented at a satellite event on the intersections of the Open Science and Social Justice agendas at OpenCon Toronto 2016, where his presentation garnered significant enthusiasm on Twitter. Leslie's presentation can be accessed on [Slideshare, here](#).

 Abby Cabunoc Mayes @abbycabs · Nov 26
Open Access: too much focus on access, need more participation. Esp from global south
[@lesliekwchan](#) #OpenCon16TO

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Leslie presenting at OpenCon, Toronto.

ELPUB 2017

Leslie has been involved with the International Conference on Electronic Publishing (ELBPUB) for many years and he is the Program Chair for the upcoming 2017 event, to be held in Cyprus. Given his position in planning the agenda and narrative for the event, we have ensured that a critical focus on processes of knowledge creation and dissemination will be central to the discussions. Also, to ensure that OCSNet members will be able to provide important project insight, we have connected this event with our final network workshop, to be held in June 2017. At the event, we also plan to have a funders roundtable and invite representatives from various funding agencies, both private and public, to discuss why and how they are supporting open science initiatives across various contexts.

The ELPUB 2017 Call for Papers, which closes on Jan. 16, 2017, can be accessed [here](#).

IDRC 2016 Networked Economies Meeting (Zanzibar)

In September 2016, Becky, from the OCSNet Coordination Team, had the opportunity to attend the annual IDRC Partners meeting, attended by project representatives from across the Networked Economies Program. The event was an incredibly useful opportunity to learn about findings and lessons emerging from other programs exploring similar themes around openness. In particular, we found great benefit in

having another opportunity to engage with the ROER4D Network, who shares a similar structure, set of values and ways of working as OCSDNet.

We feel that the Canadian government's (and hence IDRC's) renewed focus on gender in development is promising, and has ignited our own interest around the ways in which feminist theory interacts with the version of open science that we are attempting to define and pursue. Indeed, in that regard, we find that there is considerable overlap in feminist theory towards an inclusive, collaborative and localised science, and we are excited to explore these themes more thoroughly in our 'Inclusive Openness' chapter. We also look forward to receiving mentorship on gender-related themes from other network program this coming year.

6. Final Network Meeting 2017

In order to leverage the resources and attendees who will be participating at ELPUB 2017 meeting (outlined above), the OCSDNet coordination team, with feedback provided by the advisors and IDRC senior program officer, have decided to have our final network meeting in Cyprus in early June 2017. This will allow for great cost-efficiency as it will allow for our OCSDNet members to also contribute to and participate in ELPUB 2017. We also foresee very fruitful interactions between ELPUB attendees and OCSDNet members. Finally, we will also leverage the participants who will be in Cyprus for ELPUB for our final OCSDNet publication launch event.

We will be running the three day workshop at the same location where ELPUB will be held: Curium Palace Hotel (<http://www.curiumpalacehotel.com.cy/>). Other logistics and agenda planning are currently underway. We will be sending letters of invitation in early 2017.

7. Publications

[“#ScienceMustFall” Article](#)

In response to a conversation arising from the 'Fees Must Fall' student movement in South Africa, one South African student, outlining the need to decolonise higher learning institutions, declared that all of science is influenced by western modernity and “should be scratched off” entirely. Her words sparked a severe, racial and sexist backlash, gaining major national and even international attention. Given the one-sidedness of the media and the major circulation of the issue, Becky (from the OCSDNet coordination team) wrote a Medium article, outlining the serious power imbalances inherent in mainstream knowledge, and how this affects teaching and learning in South African universities. As of mid-December 2016, the article has been viewed more than 550 times and fully read 200 times.

[Stellenbosch University - tuition fee discussion](#)

Again, in South Africa, there has been considerable discussion in regards to the cost of university tuition fees, and whether or not students should be left to shoulder these costs. In particular, Stellenbosch University initiated an online forum, to engage students in innovative discussions about what can be done to help finance university education. While the entire discussion was based around cost/loan models, one

of the members of the coordination team (Becky) submitted a response to the discussion that questions why the fees cost so much to begin with; suggesting that a large portion of these fees are due to costs associated with accessing academic journal articles that are extremely expensive, despite largely funded by taxpayer dollars. This issue is well resonated in a [guest blog post by Eve Gray](#), who drawn out the historical connection of academic journal as a “neo-colonial enterprise” and how this institution continues today in the context of higher education in South Africa.

Recent OCSDNet Blogs

- **Beyond Openness: Use Of Knowledge And Public Issues In Non-Hegemonic Contexts**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/Beyond-Openness-Use-Of-Knowledges-And-Public-Issues-In-Non-Hegemonic-Contexts/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/Beyond-Openness-Use-Of-Knowledges-And-Public-Issues-In-Non-Hegemonic-Contexts/)
- **Could Transgressive Approaches To Open And Collaborative Science Contribute Towards Transformative Climate Change Adaptation?**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/Could-Transgressive-Approaches-To-Open-And-Collaborative-Science-Contribute-Towards-Transformative-Climate-Change-Adaptation/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/Could-Transgressive-Approaches-To-Open-And-Collaborative-Science-Contribute-Towards-Transformative-Climate-Change-Adaptation/)
- **Negotiating Openness: Are Participation And Access Enough?**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/Negotiating-Openness-Are-Participation-And-Access-Enough/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/Negotiating-Openness-Are-Participation-And-Access-Enough/)
- **Everyone For Themselves: When The Lack Of A Guiding Policy Framework Stifles Research Collaborations**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/Everyone-For-Themselves-When-The-Lack-Of-A-Guiding-Policy-Framework-Stifles-Research-Collaborations/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/Everyone-For-Themselves-When-The-Lack-Of-A-Guiding-Policy-Framework-Stifles-Research-Collaborations/)
- **The Meeting Of Two Worlds: Combining Traditional And Scientific Knowledge**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/The-Meeting-Of-Two-Worlds-Combining-Traditional-And-Scientific-Knowledge/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/The-Meeting-Of-Two-Worlds-Combining-Traditional-And-Scientific-Knowledge/)
- **Accessible Language: The Old-New Problem For Climate Change Adaptation In An Open Science World**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/Accessible-Language-The-Old-New-Problem-For-Climate-Change-Adaptation-In-An-Open-Science-World/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/Accessible-Language-The-Old-New-Problem-For-Climate-Change-Adaptation-In-An-Open-Science-World/)
- **Planning An Ocs Project In Lebanon – Part I**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/Planning-An-Ocs-Project-In-Lebanon-Part-I/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/Planning-An-Ocs-Project-In-Lebanon-Part-I/)
- **A Neo-Colonial Enterprise – Robert Maxwell And The Rise Of The 20th Century Scholarly Journal**
[Http://Ocsdnet.Org/A-Neo-Colonial-Enterprise-Robert-Maxwell-And-The-Rise-Of-The-20th-Century-Scholarly-Journal/](http://Ocsdnet.Org/A-Neo-Colonial-Enterprise-Robert-Maxwell-And-The-Rise-Of-The-20th-Century-Scholarly-Journal/)

Additional Publications

You can see a list of additional network publications via the link, below:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/10UXzK12_J4XpdgCAvY-KF2OU5RIcRXE0OMmv68SEAAo/edit

8. Addition of a New Research Associate

We are pleased to welcome Alejandro Posada to the OCSDNet research and coordination team in September 2016. Alejandro is a recent graduate of the IDS Co-op and Economics programs at the University of Toronto Scarborough. Alejandro has a deep interest in the political economy and financialization of the publishing industry as well as the synergies between open science and traditional knowledge systems in agriculture. In addition to contributing to all aspects of OCSDNet research, Alejandro will also focus on the links between the open source seed community and the open science communities in the global South, particularly in Latin American countries.

9. Network Coordination and Logistics

We continue to closely engage our advisors, Apiwat Ratanawaraha, Cameron Neylon, Hebe Vessuri, and Halla Thorsteinsdóttir. We had an advisory group call during the OCSDNet coordination annual planning meeting in September 2016 where we updated the advisors and sought their feedback. Notes from the call can be found here:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IKhOGEFfYE3VTwNQ6mdrcnOPV-hzP3Oa_1wA-XakFnY/edit.

The advisors will be reviewing and providing feedback to each team on the draft book chapters for the upcoming OCSDnet publication on “Contextualizing Openness” which we will be finalizing in Q1 & 2 of 2017.

Sub-grant project activities have continued as planned. After receiving several requests for no-cost extensions, we offered all projects a no-cost extension option to extend their project until June 2017. This was to ensure the projects had sufficient time to conduct thorough analyses and write-up of their projects while also participating in the Network publication and manifesto work. Eight projects have accepted the no-cost extension until June 2017 while four projects have decided to remain with the original project end date of February 2017. The four projects which will be completed in February are as follows:

- [Improving Adaptive Capacity with OCS and Participatory Governance](#)
- [Virtual Herbarium as OCS Infrastructure](#)
- [Can OCS Meet Social Needs?](#)
- [Understanding Open Hardware and Citizen Science](#)

The expenditures continue to follow the planned budget quite closely and it is expected that forecasted expenditures will remain within budget.

Network Mapping

We have structured a comprehensive network mapping analysis through a series of exercises/stages, guided by social movement, feminist, and social network literature. From a practical lens we are attempting to understand with whom and in what capacity the network is forging connections, and to what extent these interactions are enlarging the impact of our work. We would also like to understand the possibilities and challenges for future collaboration. From a theoretical lens, we are looking to understand the relationship between network, field and social movement building approaches in a collective action Open Science context. This includes an examination of the complexity of multi-actors dynamics in a setting that thrives on diversity but is also looking to establish common grounds. The network mapping analysis contributes to our main objectives and it will also be essential in structuring our final evaluation and strengthening our communications strategies, such as approaches for the dissemination of the Manifesto.

Originally we had asked the teams to identify actors and describe the type of collaboration/interactions they had with them. Our preliminary analysis showed that the network has a strong partnership with governmental bodies and policy makers as well as with local NGO involved in local research development and activism. We have now asked teams to categorize and rate actors between those that are helping advance their projects, those that have been resistant, and those that they would like to engage with in the future. The exercise will guide us in an initial understanding of the complex relationships between the various actors identified amongst the network. This will be followed by an in-depth interview process as well as a workshop in the final network meeting looking to further examine and deconstruct the power dynamics identified throughout the network mapping analysis.

Timeline

The table below indicates the activities that have been completed and those that are pending. The gray boxes indicate completed activities. Y1, Q1 begins in June 2014.

Major Project Activities	Yr 1				Yr 2				Yr 3				Yr 4*			
	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4
Phase 1: Inception (Month 1-6)																
i) Finalize conceptual framework and prepare case study selection guidelines	X															

Reports 1 & 2 to IDRC (every 6 months)																
Phase 3 Data Analysis & Write-up (Months 19-30)																
Sub-project data curation							X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Sub-project data analysis and write-up							X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Project Interim Reports to IDRC (every 6 months)							X		X		X		X			
Phase 3 Evaluation									X							
Phase 4: Consolidation (Months 31-36)																
Meta-analysis of sub-projects									X	X	X	X	X	X		
Sub-project Final Report													X	X		
OCSDNet Network Meeting & Launch of Final Publication														X		
Project Final Report to IDRC																X
Phase 4 Evaluation																X

* We have added an additional year to the timeline as per our no-cost extension request.

9. Recommendations (for IDRC)

- We would appreciate any updates/next steps about opportunities that we can inform our sub-projects about regarding IDRC's plan (as expressed during the Zanzibar 2016 meeting) to more explicitly support a gendered lens as part of research analysis.